

A Comparative Study of The Effectiveness of Risk Management Practises in the Pre and Post Merger and Acquisition (M and A) of The Selected Public Sector Bank

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Shradha Thakur
Research Scholar
Commerce
University Of Lucknow
,Uttar Pradesh

Arvind Kumar
Professor
Commerce
University Of Lucknow
LUCKNOW

Abstract The credit risk, which is defined as a lender failure to repay a loan including interest, poses a danger to the trustworthiness of commercial banks. In the year 2020, it was the alarming situation for the Government of India as NPA mushrooming at a very higher rate which instigate to introduce mega merger in the year 2020 as the M&A is the only viable option to reduce the credit risk of banks. The main objective of the study is to comparative analyse the credit risk management practices in pre and post M&A of selected public sector banks. The study further concluded that no statistically significant difference observed in pre and post M&A in relation to risk management capabilities, but still positive changes has been observed after initiation of M&A in the selected banking sector.

Keywords Merger & Acquisition(M&A), Risk Management, NPA, Financial Performance, Commercial Banks

Introduction The procedure of recognition, quantification, administering, and keeping track of probable perils that may adversely affect the performance of an organization can be described as risk management. The term risk management can also be used to describe an array of financial and operational procedures designed to mitigate the negative effects of cash flow volatility. Information gathering, analysis, risk quantification, and risk monitoring leading to risk control, risk transfer, risk reduction, risk avoidance, and risk elimination are all components of effective risk management. Risk management can also be termed as the fulfillment of different initiatives to control the undesirable aftermath of a loss or uncertainty. The banking industry has grown enormously throughout the years. Growth has brought with it a plethora of financial and non-financial risks. The banking business has expanded tremendously throughout the years. Growth has brought with it a slew of financial and non-financial hazards. Commercial banks confront risks such as credit risk, liquidity risk, operational risk, market risk, interest rate risk, transaction risk, and legal risk. This risk may have an adverse impact on a bank's bottom line. Banks' negligence for risk management was a major contributor to the Asian financial crisis of 1997, when banks were lending without collateral based on client connections. As a result, borrowers were unable to repay their debts, thus weakening the banking system. The success of business is determined by its ability to effectively it handle operational and non-operational risks. Poor risk management relates to poor financial performance. Credit risk is the most important risk in banks. Credit risk is defined as the borrower's failure, inability, or refusal to honour credit service terms and conditions. When a borrower fails to return the principle and interest, this is referred to as poor financial performance. The depositor withdrawals may jeopardise the bank's liquidity. As a result, the bank will be unable to meet its targets. Liquidity risk management is critical since it influences a bank's solvency as well as how it tackles other risks like market and credit risk. The liquid ratio is the most often used gauge of liquidity risk. The recommendations, pronouncements, and systems that banks are bound by make some commercial banks unable to comply and, as a result, look for strategies where mergers and acquisitions become the most solemn way to enhance compliance and competitiveness. Mergers and acquisitions methods promote the formation of companies with a big capital base and an appropriate liquidity ratio. It also helps companies to find a soft landing for development and diversification, tax savings, market dominance, and overall enhanced financial performance. Due to the merging of

homogeneous resources, the synergies created by mergers and acquisitions strategies also enable appropriate risk management

Aim of study

After getting through several studies associated with the subject, it has been figured out that though many researchers have concentrated on various issues connected with the risk management but still there is a considerable scope for the present study. The focal point of many researchers is to make a comparative analysis of risk management practices of selected public sector and private sector banks. None of the studies has made an effort in relation to comparatively analyse the risk management practises adopted by bank in pre and post M&A of banks. Thus, the present study is an important venture for studying, measuring, and comparing the effectiveness of risk management practices in the pre and post M&A of banks.

Objectives of Study

The main objective of the study is to comparative analyse the risk management practices in pre and post M&A of selected public sector banks. In this broader framework, the following are the specific objectives of the study:

1. To study the risk management practices adopted by the selected banks.
2. To evaluate the NPA positions in pre and post M&A of the selected banks.
3. To identify the areas where there is scope for improvement and offer suggestions which are based on findings of the study.

Review of Literature

2023 Gachigo, J., Ondigo, H., Aduda, J., & Onsomu, Z. titled "Intervening role of Risk Management on the relationship between Mergers and Acquisitions and Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya" *The study explored the intervening role of risk management on the relationship among mergers and acquisitions strategies and commercial bank financial performance. The study's findings revealed that risk management failed to mediate the relationship between mergers and acquisitions strategies and commercial bank financial performance.*

2022 titled Dahlberg, C., & Lundberg, M. "The Impact of Mergers & Acquisitions on credit- and investment risk. -Evidence from Sweden" observed that M&A increases the credit risk and inversely decreases the investment risk of the acquiring firm. Our results indicate that firm credit risk however is positively correlated with investment risk. The findings suggest that managerial hubris decreases the level of credit risk and increases the level of investment risk in acquiring firms. It is also observed from the study that acquirers with high pre-deal credit risk undertake acquisitions that decrease credit risk and increase investment risk.

2014 Oluwaremi Feyitimi titled "Merger and Acquisition as consolidation instruments for correcting the deficiencies in the banking sector" viewed that development of a sound financial system requires the collaborative efforts of the government, the monetary authorities, the operators in the industry and the general public. The study also explains that macroeconomic stability is required for the financial system to evolve and play its expected roles. enforce the confidence of all stakeholders in the banking system.

2019 Gadzo, S. G., Kportorgbi, H. K., & Gatsi, J. G. titled "Credit risk and operational risk on financial performance of universal banks in Ghana: A partial least squared structural equation model (PLS SEM) approach" This study aims to analyse the effect of credit and operational risk on the financial performance of universal banks in the context of the structural equation model (SEM) and the study showed that credit risk influences financial performance negatively contrary to the empirical study. It was also found that operational risk influences the financial performance of the universal banks in Ghana negatively.

2011 Owojori, A. A., Akintoye, I. R., & Adidu, F. A. "The challenge of risk management in Nigerian banks in the post consolidation era." This paper provide an overview of risk management practices in insured banks in Nigeria and evidenced that there is much concern in banks for return (profitability) without as much concern for risk. A better understanding and appreciation of risk are desirable in banking business where one transaction or series of transactions can put the bank out of business.

**Methodology
Sampling**

The study is purely based upon empirical research design.

The sample comprises the following set of banks that has undergone M&A in the year 2020 which are as follows:

1. Syndicate bank merged into Canara Bank
2. Oriental bank of Commerce (OBC) & United Bank of India (UBI) merged into Punjab National Bank (PNB).
3. Andhra Bank & Corporation Bank merged into Union Bank.
4. Allahabad bank merge into Indian Bank.

Tools Used

The secondary sources of data collection i.e., RBI bulletins, Annual report, manual, websites and official records of the selected banks are taken into consideration for the present study.

Statistics Used in the Study

The study employed the paired t-test to evaluate the statistically differences in relation to the effectiveness of risk management practises in pre and psot M&A of the selected bank.

Analysis

The major components of the sample banks taken for the comparatively in-depth analysis of risk management in pre and post M&A on the bank performance are Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio, Return on Asset (ROA) and Debt Recovery Ratio which are analysed as follows:

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Pre and Post M&A of the Selected Bank

S.no	Bank Name	PRE-M&A		POST M&A	
		2018	2019	2021	2022
1	Canara Bank	13..22	11.90	13.18	14.90
	Syndicate Bank	12.67	14.81		
2	PNB	9.20	9.73	14.32	14.50
	OBC	10.50	12.73		
	UBI	12.62	13.00		
3	Indian Bank	13.21	12.55	15.71	16.53
	Allahabad Bank	8.61	12.51		
4	Union Bank	10.87	11.78	12.56	14.52
	Andhra Bank	11.00	13.68		
	Corporation Bank	9.23	12.30		

Source: Compiled various Annual Reports of the Selected bank (Amount in %)

The comparative Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of selected banks in the pre and post M&A has been summarized in Table1. Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is the ratio of a bank's capital in relation to its risk weighted assets and current liabilities. As per RBI (Reserve Bank of India) norms, Indian scheduled commercial banks are required to maintain a CAR of 9% while Indian public sector banks are emphasized

to maintain a CAR of 12%. The above table exhibits that the Capital Adequacy Ratio was better in post M&A than pre-M&A of the selected bank.

Table 2. Comparative Analysis of Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio in the Pre and Post M&A of the Selected Bank

S.no	Bank Name	PRE-M&A		POST M&A	
		2018	2019	2021	2022
1	Canara Bank	7.48	5.37	3.82	2.65
	Syndicate Bank	6.28	6.16		
2	PNB	11.20	6.56	5.73	4.80
	OBC	10.48	5.93		
	UBI	16.49	8.67		
3	Indian Bank	3.81	3.75	3.37	2.27
	Allahabad Bank	8.92	5.22		
4	Union Bank	16.49	6.85	4.62	3.68
	Andhra Bank	8.42	5.73		
	Corporation Bank	8.48	5.71		

Source: Compiled various Annual Reports of the Selected bank (Amount in %)

Net NPA amount and Net NPA to Advance Ratio of the selected banks for the year 2011 to 2021 has been outlined in Table no. 4. The Net NPA to Advance ratio is considered, the lower the ratio, the better it is since lower net NPA ratio is a symptom of higher recovery rate. The above table explains that before M&A of banks, there was exponential growth of NPA but after M&A, the banks able to reduce NPA.

Table 3. Comparative Analysis of Return on Asset (ROA) in the Pre and Post M&A of the Selected Bank

S.no	Bank Name	PRE-M&A		Post M&A	
		2018	2019	2021	2022
1.	Canara Bank	-0.58	0.03	0.21	0.46
	Syndicate Bank	-0.99	-0.83		
2.	PNB	-1.60	-1.29	0.16	0.26
	OBC	-2.52	0.02		
	UBI	-1.00	1.53		

3.	Indian Bank	0.41	0.05	0.45	0.59
	Allahabad Bank	-1.88	-3.35		
4.	Union Bank	-1.08	-0.60	0.27	0.44
	Andhra Bank	-1.41	-1.12		
	Corporation Bank	-1.83	-2.97		

Source: Compiled from various Annual Reports of the Selected Bank (Amount in %)

The Table 3 explores the Return on Assets (ROA) of the selected banks was comparatively analyse in the pre and post M&A of the selected banks. The Return on Assets (ROA) is an indicator of profitability that reveals how efficiently a business can use its assets to produce more net profit ROA is a useful metric for evaluating the performance of a particular business. When a company's ROA increases over time, it suggests that the company is extracting more earnings from each dollar of assets it possesses. A falling ROA, on the other hand, indicates that a business has made poor investments, is overspending, and is likely to fail. It has been noticed from the above Table No.3 that Return on Asset was substantially improved in Post M&A than Pre-M&A of the selected Banks

Table 4. Comparative Analysis of Debt Recovery Ratio in the Pre and Post M&A of the Selected Bank

S.no	Bank Name	PRE-M&A		POST M&A	
		2018	2019	2021	2022
1.	Canara Bank	92.52	94.63	96.18	97.35
		%			
	Syndicate Bank	93.72	93.84		
2.	PNB	88.78	93.44	94.28	95.21
	OBC	89.53	94.07		
	UBI	84.59	90.74		
3.	Indian Bank	80.35	83.86	96.63	99.77
	Allahabad Bank	91.52	94.27		
4.	Union Bank	88.26	94.28	91.77	93.03
	Andhra Bank	96.19	96.25		
	Corporation Bank	91.96	94.78		

Source: Compiled from various annual reports of selected banks (Amount in %)

The Table 4 explains the comparative Debt Recovery Ratio in the pre and post M&A of the banks which was announced in the year 2020 by the government of India. The Debt Recovery Ratio is the ratio at which repayment of loan made by the borrower. The Recovery ratio determined from difference between the total advances made by the bank and Net NPA declared by the bank which is multiply with hundred. The higher ratio is preferable than lower ratio as the higher ratio indicates that bank's efficiency to recover the larger proportion of the advances from the borrowers. The Debt Recovery Ratio was significantly more favourable in Post M&A than Pre-M&A of the selected Banks .

Result and Discussion

As finding the statistically significant variations of risk management practises in pre and post M&A of the selected bank, paired t-test have been employed. The hypothesis have been formulated as under:

H0: There is no significant difference of risk management practises in the pre and post M&A of the Selected Bank

H1: There is a significant difference of risk management practises in the pre and post M&A of the Selected Bank

Table 5. Paired Sample t-test of risk management in the pre and post M&A of the Selected Bank

Pre-Post M&A of the Selected Bank	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
	0.298	5.631	1.259	-2.933	2.337	0.237	19	0.815

(Computed by the author with the help of SPSS tool version 21)

The Table 5 represents the paired t-test of the comparative pre and post M&A of the selected Bank in relation to risk management. The paired t-test was used to see if there was a significant difference in the pre and post M&A of the selected Bank. The two-tail p-value is found to be 0.815, and the two-tail t value 0.237. It indicates that there are no considerable differences found in the pre and post M&A of the selected Bank since the set alpha value is 0.05 and the p-value is more than 0.05 which reveals that the difference is non-statistically significant. Therefore, insufficient evidence found to reject null hypothesis. Thus, it is concluded that null hypothesis accepted and alternate hypothesis rejected.

Findings

Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR): The Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) has been bloomed in post M&A of the selected bank which may be resulted due to improved market capitalisation and asset quality, high level cost efficiency, reduction of the cost of operation, better business portfolio.

Net NPA to Advance Ratio: The Net NPA to Net Advance ratio was better in post M&A of the selected bank which may be resulted due to to timely assessment, quality review, assistance from the rehabilitation agency, effective appraisal of the credit worthiness of borrowers, early detection of the sign of distress assets, post credit monitoring

Return on Asset (ROA): The Return on Asset ratio was strengthen in post M&A of the selected bank which may be resulted due to the broadening capital base, security investment, improve operational efficiency, enhanced portfolio of banks, economically funding of operation, incorporation of effective and creative financial products.

Debt Recovery Ratio: The debt recovery ratio was improved in post M&A of the selected bank which may be resulted due to the transforming role of the implementation of customer interaction model, modification in the function of debt recovery, restructuring bank loan, improving asset quality base and assistance of debt collection through broaden base of expertise.

Conclusion

Thus, on the basis of above detailed discussion it has been figured out that M&A has improve the risk management capabilities in relation to Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio, Return on Asset and Debt Recovery Ratio. But such

- improvement was statistically insignificant to prove that significant variation of risk management practises found in pre and post M&A of the selected banks.
- Suggestions for the future Study**
1. Initiative must be made to improve the quality of advances and recovery process for broadening bank's credit.
 2. The evaluation of credit assessment through training and counselling of employees which may resulted to lower NPA declaration made by bank.
 3. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI), a central regulating bank in India, should devise the policies, measure and practises that help to bank's NPA should not exceed more than the tolerable limit.
 4. Before taking any strategic decision regarding merger, the Government should consider the bank risk which reduces the integrated financial performance of merged entity.
 5. The banks which have high credit risk should be merge with low credit risk as low credit risk faced by banks have efficient techniques to reduce the risk.
- Limitation of the Study**
1. The study based on secondary data derived from RBI bulletin, websites and annual reports of selected banks.
 2. There are many approaches and parameters to evaluate the efficiency of selected banks which may result in the variation of findings.
 3. The present study takes into consideration four years viz. 2 years prior to M&A and two-year post M&A as the M&A took place in the year 2020.
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